

MODELLING OF RECYCLED CARBON FIBRE-REINFORCED 3D-PRINTED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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CARBON FIBRE RECYCLING PATHWAYS

Fibre reuse

Direct moulding	Additive manufacturing	SMC/BMC	Nonwoven technology	Tape technology		Spinning technology
Injection moulding	Reinforced filament FFF	Compression moulding	Dry / Wet process	HiPerDiF	Carding	Warp / Flyer / Friction / Other
Application Modelling Homogenization			Quasi-isotropic nonwovens	Oriented tapes		Hybrid yarns

Recycled CFRP products

Papon, E. A. et al. Process optimization and stochastic modeling of void contents and mechanical properties in additively manufactured composites. Composites Part B: Engineering, 107325. (2019)

Additive manufacturing in composite tooling

<https://airtech3d.com/print-tech>

Functional prototypes, Low-volume manufacturing

<https://www.9tlabs.com/case-studies/helicopter-door-hinge>

Modelling

Properties:

Bead level uncertainty

(fibre length, orientation, volume fraction, fibre and matrix modulus, interfacial shear, void content)

Lamina level uncertainty

(lamina modulus, bead diffusion length, void content, elastic constants, thermal conductivity)

FFF process variables

(temperature, print speed, nozzle diameter)

Physical model:

- MROM
- Void model
- Homogenization
- CLT

DETERMINATION OF MODEL INPUTS

Filament production:

- Teluran GP35 ABS + vCF/rCF 10; 20 m/m%
- Twin screw extruder (Labtech - LTE 26-44)
- Filament diameter: \varnothing 1,75 mm

Speciment production:

- Table temperature: 90-110°C
- Nozzle temperature: 220-250°C
- 0-90° layers, 100% infill

Characterisation:

- Tensile testing
- Fibre content
- Residual fibre length
- Fibre orientation – ellipsometry

Parameters:

FLD, FOD, E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , G_{12} , UTS

Adeniran O. et al. Material design factors in the additive manufacturing of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic Composites: A state-of-the-art review, Advances in Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering, 100100. (2022)

If you are interested, do not hesitate to visit my poster:

P010

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Thank you for your attention!

